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Social Media and its impact on product branding in Bangladesh

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Abstract: In today's competitive business world, for surviving business needs proper branding. Branding is essential to every industry regardless of the size because it helps distinguish a company from its competitors. Product branding is not free of cost; it is tough for enterprises, especially Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) of Bangladesh, to carry out a successful product branding program through traditional marketing activities. However, social media has evolved over the last few years to become the most affordable for product branding. Nowadays, social media is among the 'best possibilities available' to an item to get in touch with potential customers. Social networking websites are the method to interact socially. Promoters are considering many different social media possibilities and beginning to apply new social projects at a higher rate than ever before. There is no universal product branding strategy suitable for all companies, but the appropriate one may be built according to the company goals and means. Social media, especially facebook, is becoming an excellent tool for B2C product branding. Recently booming of internet users in Bangladesh is enhancing this opportunity for all sizes of companies. They can enjoy the benefit of social media to promote the product brand cost-effectively if they overcome the current challenges. This paper discusses the ideas of social media and social media promotion, other aspects like the development and advantages, role and benefits of medial social branding, perspective, and importance of social media in publicity, social media promotion methods. It also presents an outline of social media promotion in Bangladesh.

Keywords: Social Media, Branding Product, Social media promotion, Digital Marketing, Social media promotion in Bangladesh, Internet.

I. Introduction

In recent years the online environment is viewed by users from a new perspective in a commercial way. With social media, consumers can interact instantly with brands and share opinions on the

products they are interested in. It is the inherent nature of consumers to buy products that are recommended by friends, family members, relatives, and someone they know in real life or even in the virtual world.

Social media represents the online content publicly created and available to end-users. It is becoming one of the main tools used to spread information among customers. Blogs, social networking sites, content communities, virtual worlds, or collaborative projects all represent groups of people that create and share content inside and outside of professional routines. For marketers, this phenomenon is of high interest as social media is becoming an essential source of customer information sharing, awareness, support, and empowerment (Kaplan and Haenlein, 2010)[1,18]. Consequently, social media allows businesses to effectively and inexpensively engage in direct client contact, reaching levels of efficiency undoubtedly higher than any other traditional marketing communication tool (Berthon et al., 2008)[2].

The recent statistics from different sources show that social media is becoming an essential part of everyday life. The results from these statistics are astonishing. As of July 2015, every day 1 million new active mobile social media users are added, which is 12 per second (brand watch). They also measured that 91% of retail brands use two or more social media channels. All these facts don't even leave a doubt about how fast is social media emerging in the business sector and peoples' lives.

Although traditional forms of brand communication via TV, radio, or newspaper advertising achieved great success in the past, their effectiveness is decreasing drastically in today's more customer-dominated business environment. Virgin America, Inc., a United States-based airline, is spending nearly 70% of its total marketing budget in digital and emerging social media platforms (Frazier 2011)[3]. Converse, American footwear and apparel brand, is one step ahead in spending its marketing budget beyond traditional media. Less than 10% of Converse's spend is on conventional media (Frazier, 2011)[3,4].

There are many pieces of evidence and examples of how companies use social media for more efficient communication and better results. As of the second quarter of 2016, facebook had 1.71 billion monthly active users, and there are 50 million dynamic business pages (brand watch). Marketers should, therefore, become more and more aware of the importance of these platforms and the information spread throughout them.

II. Literature Review

The term “Social Media” refers to the newer platforms of online technologies that are used by large groups of people to interact with each other for sharing information, opinions, knowledge, and interests. According to Kaplan and Haenlein (2010)[5,6], Social Media is a group of Internet-based applications that build on the ideological and technological foundations of Web 2.0, and that allow the creation and exchange of User Generated Content. In the business world, social media is known as consumer-generated media (Mangold and Faulds, 2009)[7]. Social media comes in many different forms today. The most popular formats of social media are blogs (Blogger, Typepad, WordPress), microblogs (Tumblr, Twitter), social networks (Facebook, Google+, Hi5, LinkedIn, Myspace, XING), video-sharing sites (Dailymotion, Metacafe, Vimeo, YouTube), photo-sharing sites (Flickr, Photobucket, Shutterfly), presentation-sharing sites (authorSTREAM, Scribd, SlideShare), social bookmarking sites (Delicious, Digg, Reddit, StumbleUpon), review sites (Citysearch, TripAdvisor, Yelp), virtual worlds (ActiveWorlds, Second Life), and Wikis (Wetpaint, Wikipedia, Wikia).

According to American Marketing Association (2014)[8,9], a brand is a name, term, design, symbol, or any other feature that identifies one seller’s good or service as distinct from those of other sellers. Since a brand is one of the most valuable intangible assets of every business, the success of companies largely depends on communicating brands with customers.

The unique aspects of social media and its immense popularity have revolutionized marketing practices such as advertising and promotion (Hanna, Rohn, and Crittenden, 2011) Social media has also influenced consumer behavior from information acquisition to post-purchase behavior such as dissatisfaction statements or behaviors about a product or a company. (Mangold and Faulds, 2009)[10].

Communication of brand/company and users help create a favorable or less favorable image of other users who read the information posted and consider them in the information or purchase. Interactivity with the target brand in social media is perceived differently by consumers depending on the message they convey (Shin, 2008)[11]. The perceived risk of purchasing and how much money are willing to pay for a product also determines the user to think more about the quality and the utility of the product. (Ioanas, 2012)[12].

Urde & Greyser (2014) combined brand identity, communication, and brand reputation in the so-called ‘Corporate Brand Identity and Reputation Matrix’ (CBIRM). In this context, the communication layer within the model functions as a catalyst that decodes a strategically defined brand identity in operational measures, which ideally results in a positive brand reputation among

multiple stakeholders.

Figure 1: Corporate brand identity & reputation matrix (Adapted from Urde & Greyser by C. Hoffmann & L. Weithaler, 2015)

III. Research Methodology

Selecting a proper method for analyzing the proposed topic is important for reaching the aim of a study. This study is based on different sources of data. At first, the use of the Internet in marketing research was only a new source of information. Now the research can be done directly, not just surveys, but qualitative research as in-depth interviews and focus groups. (Stoica, 2011)[13].

Time is changing as well as technology is continuously improving. Companies need to stay in the game and use any new opportunity to improve sales, marketing, and customer loyalty. Technology gives consumers the power to investigate products. Therefore many companies today have pages on social networks to supplement information held about products.

Consumers have much more tendency to relate with a company after they read various reviews and comments of the consumers who have already purchased these products. By using social media, consumers have the power to influence other buyers through reviews.

For example, instead of buying a product that he knows very little, consumers have become new researchers. Before making a purchase, many consumers read what other people think about a particular product by logging in to an account on a social networking site. Social media users trust in what they believe their friends, family, and even strangers on these networks. Many online buyers consider social sites as being a valuable and reliable source for researching products and services.

This research tries to offer answers to some usual questions as: What is the role of social media? Is social media playing a role in promoting product branding? Do the consumers appreciate the opportunity to link with an online brand? Is social media playing a role in purchasing decisions? Therefore, it aims to study the impact of social media on product branding, consumers, and the choices they make in the online environment.

Secondary data is best known as a methodology for doing research using pre-existing statistical data (Heaton, 2004). It is a research strategy using pre-existing quantitative or qualitative research data for the reasons for investigating new questions or verifying previous studies (Heaton, 2004)[14].

Social media is an entirely new and emerging technology in Bangladesh. Content analysis, desk research, and reliance on literature were based on books, journals, articles, trade publications, newspapers, and magazines. Besides, web-based information was thoroughly extracted and analyzed for statistical representation. Data collection was also conducted through relevant documents concerning the research's overall goal. Several reports were collected from internet that provide useful information regarding social media product branding in Bangladesh.

IV. Social media

Social media is the most straightforward way to engage with customers in online. According to Wikipedia, social media is internet-based resources for sharing and discussing details among humans. Community social networking websites are all about social networking as well as social networking in a way that espouses believe in among parties and areas engaged. Any website which allows the customer to discuss their material, views, and motivates connections and group

developing can be classified as social media. Most popular social media websites are Facebook or FB, YouTube, Twitter, MySpace, Stumble Upon, Delicious, Scribed, Flickr, etc.

Wikipedia has a standard definition of the term: Community Press is the democratization of details, transforming people from material visitors into material publishers. It is the move from a broadcast mechanism to a many-to-many model, rooted in discussions between authors, people, and colleagues.

Social media is the way to interact socially with mass people. They use web based technology to spread information and details to the customers quickly. Social media symbolizes low-cost resources that are used to combine technology and social connections with the use of terms. Andreas Kaplan and Michael Haenlein determine social media as "a team of Internet-based applications that develop the ideological and technological foundations of Web 2.0, which allows the development and return of user-generated material." There are two advantages of social media that are essential to companies, they include:

- Cost decrease by decreasing staff time.
- Increase of probability of revenue creation.

A Role of social media in product banding

Social media is now becoming an integral part of political strategies, national defense methods, public policy, advertising, item management and even intra organization interaction. The major task of social media is to inform customers about the company's product. Social promotion plays a natural aspect in promotion.

- Social media can be used to provide an identity about the companies and the items or solutions that they provide.
- Social media can be useful for creating connections with those who might not otherwise know about the items or support or what the companies represent.
- Social media creates companies "real" to customers. If they want people follow them they need not just talk about the newest item information, but discuss their character with them.
- Social media can be used to affiliate themselves with their colleagues that may be serving the same concentrate on industry.
- Social media can be used to connect and provide the connections that customers look for.

B Benefits of social media product banding

They are different from conventional promotion methods with social media product banding. social media product banding offers distinct advantages. It provides a window to marketers not only present items / solutions to clients but also to pay attention to customer’s grievances and suggestions. Social media product banding allows marketers to recognize various professional categories or influencers among various categories. Social media product banding is nearly zero prices (as compared to conventional client outreach programs) as most of the social media websites are free.

Social media promotion allows in:

- Generating exposure to companies.
- Increasing traffic/subscribers.
- Building new organization partnerships.
- Development of internet search engine results positioning positions.
- Generating qualified brings due to better prospecting projects.
- Selling more solutions and items.
- Reduction in overall promotion expenses.

V. Social Media in Bangladesh

In the first time in 1996 Bangladeshi people got the opportunity to use internet. Internet was launched in June, 1996. After internet was launched, national poll results were made available to the netizens of the web using World Wide Web. This was the first ever usage event of its kind in Bangladesh. The effort was appreciated in many corners especially among the Bangladeshis living abroad. (Hamidur, 2009)[15,16,18]. Gradually Bangladeshi people become introduced with different usages internet, though a large number of people do not have access to internet till today. Today internet users of Bangladesh use social networking sites than any other applications.

Table 6-1: Top ten internet countries in Asia

ASIA INTERNET USE, POPULATION DATA AND FACEBOOK STATISTICS - JUNE 2016						
Rank	Country	Population (2016 Est.)	Internet Users, (Year 2000)	Internet Users 30-Jun-2016	Penetration (% Population)	Facebook 30-Jun-2016

1.	China	1,378,561,591	22,500,000	721,434,547	52.3 %	1,800,000
2.	India	1,266,883,598	5,000,000	462,124,989	36.5 %	157,000,000
3.	Indonesia	258,316,051	2,000,000	132,700,000	51.4 %	88,000,000
4.	Japan	126,464,583	47,080,000	115,111,595	91.0 %	26,000,000
5.	Bangladesh	162,855,651	100,000	63,290,000	38.9 %	21,000,000
6.	Philippines	102,624,209	2,000,000	54,000,000	52.6 %	54,000,000
7.	Vietnam	95,261,021	200,000	49,063,762	51.5 %	40,000,000
8.	Korea, South	49,180,776	19,040,000	45,314,248	92.1 %	17,000,000
9.	Thailand	68,200,824	2,300,000	41,000,000	60.1 %	41,000,000
10.	Pakistan	192,758,348	133,900	34,342,400	17.8 %	27,000,000

Source: *Internet World Stats*

According to CNN report on January 26, 2015 the top five most popular social networking sites in Bangladesh are,

Facebook: Facebook is planet's most prevalent long range interpersonal communication site. It is ranked on 1st number in the list of top five best social networking websites in Bangladesh. There is no device that does not has an inherent Facebook application in it. Facebook was made by Mark Zuckerberg in 2004[17] and now it has a large number of clients all around the globe. Designers continue working day and night to keep it up to the necessities of its clients.

Twitter: It is ranked on 2nd number in the list of top five best social networking websites in Bangladesh. Twitter is an extremely mainstream micro-site its clients can accompany whom they need to take after incorporating businesspeople on- screen characters, performers, models or any of their top picks stars and companions. Similarly, user can impart their emotions to the companions in 160 words which twitter calls a 'tweet'.

LinkedIn: It is ranked on 3rd number in the list of top five best social networking websites in Bangladesh. It is tremendously well known around the business class and that is the reason the top executives and presidents of extraordinary organizations have their profiles on this site. It is the best interpersonal interaction webpage for the individuals who need to occupations as their profile

will function as CV and individuals can offer them employments through this informal communication site

Pinterest: Despite the fact that it has not been quite a while that Pinterest was presented however it has made its name as a result of the prosperity of the android telephones. It is ranked on 4th number in the list of top five best social networking websites in Bangladesh. The clients can make a pinboard and stick any life occasion or photographs on their pin board.

Friendcircle: It is ranked on 5th number in the list of top five best social networking sites in Bangladesh. Friendcircle was made by Mutalib Raza in April 2014. Friendcircle (<https://friendcircle.co>) is mostly popular in Bangladeshi college students. They use friendcircle to share their picture, stories; also they can upload music or videos too.

Although internet penetration rate in Bangladesh is marked very low, a big online community is gradually developing. According to Bangladesh Telecommunication Regulatory Commission (BTRC) 80 percent internet users of Bangladesh are on social networking website Facebook. It has more than 26 million users on January 2017 with 16% penetration rate. A major portion of this internet community is using social media regularly. However, the most visited web sites in Bangladesh (in accordance with their rank) are shown in the table below:

Table 6-1: Top the most visited web sites in Bangladesh

Rank	Name of the Sites
1.	facebook.com
2.	google.com.bd
3.	google.com
4.	youtube.com
5.	prothom-alo.com
6.	banglanews24.com
7.	yahoo.com
8.	blogspot.com
9.	bdnews24.com
10.	ask.com

Source: Alexa (2014)

A Bangladeshi Brands on Social Media

As social media brand-building power grows, it no longer makes sense to treat it as an experiment. That is the reason companies in Bangladesh are coming forward to have their strong and active presence on social media. Even some big companies are recruiting social media managers for managing their pages on social media and interacting with the page members (clients) actively. Social media principles and guidelines have also been enacted in some companies for their executives.

B Top Brands of Bangladesh on Facebook

Facebook is an American profit oriented corporation. It is an online social media and social networking service based in Menlo Park, California. The Facebook website was launched on February 4, 2004. Mark Zuckerberg, along with his four fellow Harvard College students and roommates are built Facebook as social platform. Facebook has more than 1.79 billion monthly active users as of January, 2017 and it is the most popular social networking site in the world, based on the number of active user accounts.

Facebook allows millions of its users to connect and interact with each other. Facebook has also the opportunity for companies to create their official page and to engage customer talking about their brands. Today’s customers would like to connect and interact with the businesses whose services they want. Among the top most visited sites in Bangladesh, facebook is holding the number one position as described before. The following table shows the most popular official fan pages of different brands in Bangladesh on Facebook:

Table 6-2: Top facebook fan page (total fans)

Rank	Official Page Name	Brand	Industry	Local Fans	International Fans	Total Fans
1.	Grameenphone	grameenphone	Telecommunication	9437728	514767	9952495
2.	Robi Axiata Limited	robi	Telecommunication	8833910	422059	9255969
3.	Banglalink Digital	banglalink	Telecommunication	8251053	2226087	8673470
4.	Airtel Buzz	airtel buzz	Telecommunication	6447383	3574916	6780356
5.	Samsung Mobile Bangladesh	SAMSUNG	Mobile, Smart phone, Tablet	3205440	552562	3665838

Source: Social bakers, January 2017

C Top Brands of Bangladesh on Twitter

Millions of people around the world use Twitter to discuss everything from the news to brands and businesses. At present, there are 313 million monthly active users on Twitter worldwide (as of January, 2017). And those users post an average of 500 million Tweets every day. Short message services of Twitter are called Tweets. Registered users on Twitter can read and post or re-tweets, but unregistered users can only read them. According to few statistics Twitter is one of the top five social networking sites in Bangladesh. Companies can use Twitter to connect directly with people (followers/ customers) who are interested in their brand, participate in real-time events and conversations, enhance the online brand personality and thus delight the customers. The following table shows the most popular official Twitter accounts of different brands in Bangladesh.

Table 6-3: Top twitter accounts (total followers)

Rank	Official Profile Name	Brand	Industry	Total Followers
1	@Grameenphone	grameenphone	Telecommunication	123132
2	@TweetRobi	robi	Telecommunication	45399
3	@airtelbuzz	airtel buzz	Telecommunication	37710
4	@BanglaSong	music.com.bd	Bangla music	18171
5	@banglalinkmela	banglalink mela	Telecommunication	13094

Source: Socialbakers, January 2017

D Top Brands of Bangladesh on YouTube

Founded in February 2005, YouTube allows billions of people to discover, watch, and share originally-created videos. YouTube provides a forum for people to connect, inform, and inspire others across the globe and acts as a distribution platform for original content creators and advertisers (YouTube, 2014). It has 1 billion monthly active users who are watching over 6 billion hours of video each month on YouTube, that's almost an hour for every person on earth (January, 2017).

Due to limited internet speed YouTube are still suffering to get popularity among the mass people of Bangladesh. Though it has no position on the top most visited social networking sites in Bangladesh, marketers and companies are trying to establish their own brands channel in YouTube as a substitute of most popular traditional marketing channel television.

The following table shows the most popular YouTube channels of different brands in Bangladesh (according to the total number of views of the videos).

Table 6-4: Top YouTube channels (total video views)

Rank	Official Channel Name	Brand	Industry	Subscribers	Total Video Views
1	Closeup Bangladesh	closeup	Personal care	51890	15544488
2	Airtel Buzz	airtel buzz	Telecommunication	69143	14913648
3	Robi Axiata Limited	robi	Telecommunication	27562	14762653
4	banglalink digital	banglalink	Telecommunication	12081	10590072
5	Grameenphone	grameenphone	Telecommunication	30918	9986903

Source: Socialbakers, January 2017

VI. Conclusion

If a company wants to have a successful online presence today, social media marketing is most important. It is one of the most popular, influential, and promising means of product branding way which every company in Bangladesh must embrace. In this study, an attempt was undertaken to depict the using of social media in product branding. With the uptrend in both the number and engagement of users, social media is going to be a big online community in Bangladesh. Companies doing business in Bangladesh can grab the attractive economic benefits of social media identified throughout the study. This study also depicts that social media is not a risk-free platform. Casual dabbling with social media content would not ensure the target benefits for the companies. Since fans, followers, and subscribers are free to post their comments on these platforms, businesses are also susceptible to the possibility of negative publicity. To do so, companies are suggested to appoint executives who will be responsible for developing and maintaining content in social media. Businesses should also align other resources with their social media marketing strategies so that they can ensure the attention and frequent communication needed to embrace social media effectively.

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